

Introduction

Welcome to the **third edition** of the Diamond OA (OA) Expertise Center's newsletter! It has been an exciting period: the Mapping and Monitoring project has just published a curated list of Diamond OA journals in the Netherlands, and the Expertise Centre has released a report on a survey on attitudes of researchers to Diamond OA in the Netherlands. Keep reading for more updates!

The Team ([Bregt](#), [Femke](#), [Juliana](#), [Maria](#), and [Erica](#))

News & Resources

A CURATED LIST OF DIAMOND OA JOURNALS IN THE NETHERLANDS

mapping and monitoring diamond open access

The "Mapping and Monitoring Diamond OA in the Netherlands" project has just released a **curated list of Diamond OA journals in the Netherlands**. The list offers authors, librarians, open access advisors, open science communities, and policy makers a reliable overview of **Dutch academic journals that publish open access, charge no mandatory fees to authors or readers, and are controlled by academic and not-for-profit research communities**. For more information on sources and the criteria for inclusion and exclusion, see the About and Readme tabs in the spreadsheet.

ATTITUDES OF RESEARCHERS TO DIAMOND OA: A SURVEY REPORT

The survey results first previewed at our "Developing a Diamond Open Access Discovery Kit" event in May are now officially published! The report, authored by [Lena Ryzhova](#) and [Benedetta Siviero](#) presents a **national snapshot of how researchers in the Netherlands perceive Diamond OA**. It explores **awareness levels, publishing practices, and barriers to adoption**, with particular attention to early- and late-stage career researchers as well as disciplinary differences. The findings highlight both **the promise of Diamond OA and the structural changes needed to support its wider integration**.

KICK-OFF MEETING WITH AMBASSADORS

As a kick-off event, we organised a first in-person meeting with our [ambassadors](#), hosted by our generous partner **SURF** in Utrecht. After a brief introduction round, during which ideas began to flow, we discussed **possible projects and activities for the near future**. We will soon be able to present the first results of activities developed during the meeting. We are convinced that with this fantastic group of scholars, we will be able to discover new ways and paths to grow our Diamonds.

APPLYING THE DIAMOND OPEN ACCESS STANDARD

We received the results of the DOAS self-assessment tools from the Netherlands University Presses (NUP) and started conversations around the DOAS in Q1 and Q2 of 2025. Going forward, the expertise center will look at the **Diamond OA sustainability check** with NUPs. The Expertise Centre will also propose **workshops and events** to exchange knowledge in areas where NUPs need support, besides the resource materials provided. Until the end of the year, the aim is also to **extend the activities to other service providers or societies in the Netherlands** interested in the DIAMAS self-assessments.

In the Spotlight

- The **Diamond OA Journal of Trial and Error** is having a **symposium** on the role of failure and uncertainty in research on October 7th at the Utrecht University Museum.
- **Jos Baeten**, one of our Diamond OA ambassadors, has published a chapter in Smart Humanity (vol. 2) on "**Access to scientific knowledge**." Find the original Dutch version alongside an English translation [here](#).
- **EDCH Training Platform**. Discover tailored training modules designed to support capacity-building by Diamond OA Publishing Services and Technology Providers—all free to access!
- **DIAMAS Policy Brief**. Read about the recommendations by the DIAMAS project after the second phase of the project ("Improving coordination, quality and sustainability of IPSP") in this policy brief.

Please provide your **feedback** on the **Diamond OA Expertise Centre** website by answering **anonymously** to [this survey](#) (only composed of 8 questions!).

Agenda

- **October 6-8:** CRAFT-OA Conference. Göttingen, DE.
- **October 17:** NRIN Symposium. Wereldmuseum, Leiden.
- **October 21:** OIPA Online Symposium. Online.
- **October 24:** National Open Science Festival. University of Groningen.
- More events can be found [here](#).

Advertise your event
by sending us an
[email](#).

SAVE THE DATE!
OCTOBER 28, 2025, 12:00-13:30
LAUNCH OF THE NETHERLANDS OA BOOKS COMMUNITY

The focus of the webinar will be on the **sustainability of book publishing in the Netherlands**. There will be a **panel discussion**, moderated by [Bregt Lameris](#), with confirmed speakers [Annie van den Oever](#), [Dan Hassler Forest](#), and [Erna Sattler](#) (and more to be announced!). Keep posted on our LinkedIn and our agenda for details on registration for the event.